

ELECTROCHEMICAL CO₂ REDUCTION IN MODERN ENERGY AS A METHOD OF PRODUCTION OF PROPANOL AND OTHER ALTERNATIVE FUELS

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Abstract. The article describes the basic aspects of the electrochemical carbon dioxide reduction process and the catalysts and electrolytes used in it. It is followed by a discussion of the application of this technology, discussing possible conversion products. The process of electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide, given the current progress in its development, appears to be a promising way to manage this gas, especially given current trends related to the decarbonization of many industries and the search for new methods of disposing of CO₂. Since the invention of the technology, advances in reactor design and the discovery of new catalysts have made the process - given the right parameters - economically viable for simple products such as carbon monoxide and formic acid. However, further research work is needed before the process can find industrial application in the production of particularly desirable hydrocarbons such as propanol and ethylene.

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy transition is one of the most demanding challenges of the modern world. Moving away from fossil fuels will require not only an increase in the capacity of well-known renewable technologies (i.e. solar and wind farms), but may also require the large-scale implementation of many other solutions that are still developing. Despite many efforts by governments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, they remain high, and it is unlikely that ambitious climate targets will be achieved without further changes in the industrial sector. As stated in [1], in 2023, the power sector was responsible for emission of 14.8 Gt of CO₂, and to achieve the net-zero emission target by 2050, a reduction by more than half is required.

One of the future energy technologies is electrochemical CO₂ reduction (CO₂RR), which, although initially not developed due to low process efficiencies, is currently under intensive development; mainly due to the advancement of modern solutions, i.e. high-temperature electrolyzers. According to [2] – SOEC technology offers significantly higher efficiency, regardless of the performance measure chosen (Faraday efficiency, cell voltage, resistance specific to a given area, energy efficiency or electricity consumption). The high conversion efficiency has been verified in industrially relevant stack sizes, for which the active surface area > 8000 cm².

This technology is still developing and has many significant drawbacks compared to other methods of CO₂ reduction and classic methods of obtaining carbon monoxide and hydrocarbons. The main challenges fac-

ing the electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide include high investment costs and low current densities [3], as well as the need to use expensive catalysts. The issue of scalability of systems for commercial purposes is also important; the authors of [3] draw attention to:

- different reaction kinetics and mass transfer for laboratory and large-scale electrolyzers, leading to differences in operating parameters,
- difficulty in optimal transport of mass and electric charge due to the increase in cell surface,
- reactant distribution problem, increased ohmic losses and reduced catalyst utilization.

In addition, there are also difficulties to be solved in the process itself, i.e. [4]:

- product separation, as unreacted carbon dioxide is mixed with carbon monoxide, requiring a separation process, e.g. pressure swing adsorption;
- electricity costs – as the authors note, a price change of 0.01 \$/kWh in the production of n-propanol changes the net present value of the entire investment by almost 40 million USD.

2. MECHANISMS

2.1. Electrochemical reduction

The electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction is performed in electrochemical reactors (EC). A typical reactor system consists of an anode and cathode, a membrane and an electrolyte.

For the process to take place, the electrodes are connected to an external DC source. The reduction reaction, i.e. the joining of electrons by the substance being

reduced, takes place at the cathode connected to the negative pole. Oxidation, on the other hand, takes place at the anode connected to the positive pole, where electrons are removed. In order to close the current circuit, the electrodes are immersed in an electrolyte solution that allows the charges to flow. However, to ensure that the reaction products do not mix, the cathode and anode are separated by an ion-selective membrane.

The reduction of CO₂ in an aqueous electrolyte solution can yield a number of compounds, including carbon monoxide CO, formic acid HCOOH, methane CH₄, methanol CH₃OH, ethylene C₂H₄, ethanol C₂H₅OH, or n-propanol C₃H₇OH [27, 4], according to the reactions:

The distribution of the products obtained depends mainly on the type of electrode used [5], the type and concentration of electrolyte, [6], and the voltage [6], as well as the process parameters: pressure and temperature [7].

A key parameter related to the operation of an electrochemical reactor is its selectivity, also referred to as Faraday efficiency η_{FE}^i . It defines the ratio between the number of moles of the i -th substance formed and the maximum amount theoretically possible at a given charge. A high selectivity for the i -th reduction product means that it is the main product of the process. The second key parameter is the current density I , which determines the rate of the reaction taking place. The partial current density I_i , on the other hand, determines the rate of formation of the i -th product. For the CO₂RR process to find industrial application, the parameter values η_{FE}^i and I_i should exceed approximately 90% and 300 mA/cm², respectively [8].

While electrochemical reduction of CO₂ can yield many industrially desirable substances and fuels while capturing the greenhouse gas, the process itself still struggles with a number of limitations. One of the main problems is the low solubility of CO₂ in water and the associated limitations in mass transport [9]. A solution to this problem may be the use of gas diffu-

sion electrodes, in which CO₂ is directed to the reduction zone directly in gaseous form [10]. In addition, greater reduction efficiency can be achieved using a zero-gap configuration [11]. This type of system has no catholyte flow channel and the cathode is in direct contact with the membrane, which lowers the module resistance and allows higher current densities.

2.2. Photoelectrochemical reduction

One of the key drawbacks of CO₂RR is the high voltage required between the electrodes [12], which increases the energy intensity of the process. The external energy requirement can be reduced or eliminated by using photoelectrochemical reduction.

Photoelectrochemical reactors use solar energy as a source of process driving energy. There are three main types of this device [13]: (I) PV-EC reactors, in which the external energy source is a photovoltaic module, (II) PEC reactors, in which electrodes are replaced by semiconductor photoelectrodes and the incident radiation drives the reaction, and (III) PV-PEC reactors, equipped with both photoelectrodes and a PV module.

Due to the high technological maturity of PV modules and EC devices, the most promising photoelectrochemical reactor technology is currently PV-EC [14]. While PEC-type devices are characterised by greater simplicity [15], they currently achieve lower efficiencies [13].

2.3. Tandem reduction

Some of the most desirable products of CO₂ reduction are C₂₊ hydrocarbons, such as n-propanol or ethanol. However, the predominant reduction products are simpler C₁ compounds, and obtaining higher hydrocarbons is proving challenging. Higher yields of C₂₊ products are possible when, in place of CO₂, the substance being reduced is CO, which is a reaction intermediate [16-18]. As the selectivities achieved for the reduction of CO₂ to CO exceed 90% [13], the separation of the two processes can be beneficial in terms of overall efficiency. Reactors in which CO₂ is initially reduced to CO and then CO to C₂₊ compounds are called tandem reactors.

The paper [16] compared the reduction of CO₂ and CO in the same EC reactor. The maximum selectivities for ethylene, ethanol and propanol were 14%, 6% and 4% for CO₂, respectively, while for CO they were 28%, 13% and 23%, respectively. The paper [19] presented the results of CO₂ reduction in a tandem reactor, and the maximum selectivity to C₃H₇OH was 15.9%.

Similarly to CO₂ reduction, an important drawback limiting reactor performance is the low solubility of CO in water [20], hence systems using gas diffusion electrodes are also being investigated [17]. Furthermore, the need to purify the gas stream between reactor stages increases the complexity and cost of the system.

3. CATALYSTS AND ELECTROLYTES USED

3.1. Catalysts

A catalyst for a chemical reaction is a substance that modifies the process in such a way that certain molecules receive energy to participate in the reaction, which in practice usually translates into a reduction in the duration of the process.

For the CO₂RR reaction, the best Faraday efficiencies for reduction to CO are achieved for gold, zinc and silver; respectively: 87.1%, 81.5%, and 79.4% [5]. Both catalysts and electrolytes have an important influence on the CO₂RR reaction. As noted in [21], the efficiency of the reaction largely depends on the structure of the electrical double layer, both in terms of electrode and electrolyte type. Since the CO₂RR reduction reaction requires a higher potential than that implied by the equilibrium potential, this overpotential can result in an increased hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), which competes with the CO₂ reduction and reduces the CO selectivity [22].

The product that can be obtained with high selectivity in the CO₂RR process is formic acid, with η_{FE}^{HCOOH} exceeding 90% [26]. The best results were obtained for catalysts using, among others, bismuth [23,28] and tin [24]. Furthermore, current density values close to those found in industrial applications have been achieved. In [28], $I_{HCOOH}=450$ mA/cm² and $\eta_{FE}^{HCOOH}=97\%$ were achieved. Also in [24], high parameters of $I_{HCOOH}=421$ mA/cm² with $\eta_{FE}^{HCOOH}=91.1\%$ were achieved. In addition, the catalysts tested had good stability and retained their parameters when operated for longer periods of time. In [28] this was 100 h, while in the [23] $\eta_{FE}^{HCOOH}>70\%$ was maintained for more than 1000 h.

Methane is also a product that can be successfully obtained by the CO₂RR process. The selectivities achieved reach values in the order of 80-85% [29]. Copper-based catalysts show good results [30, 31]. In [30], a selectivity of 77% was achieved at $I_{CH_4}=525$ mA/cm². Meanwhile, in the work [31], the selectivity was 82% at 391 mA/cm². In addition, the work demonstrated more than 10 hours of stable operation with satisfactory $\eta_{FE}^{CH_4}$

Methanol can also be obtained with high selectivity, exceeding 70% [32]. However, the achieved current densities I_{CH_3OH} are presently relatively low and in only a few works [33,34] exceed 100 mA/cm². The highest current density of 129 mA/cm² was achieved in [34], where selectivity exceeded 40% for a cobalt-based catalyst. In [33], $I_{CH_3OH}=122.7$ mA/cm² was

achieved with $\eta_{FE}^{CH_3OH}=67.4\%$, for a catalyst comprising doped copper.

Lower CO₂RR selectivity is observed for C₂ products such as ethanol and ethylene. The only metallic catalyst currently studied capable of efficiently reducing CO₂ to C₂₊ compounds is copper and its derivatives [35], due to its efficiency in forming bonds between carbon atoms [17] and its ability to absorb CO on the catalyst surface [35].

The highest parameters for CO₂RR to ethylene, i.e. $\eta_{FE}^{C_2H_4}=49.1\%$ at $I_{C_2H_4}=491$ mA/cm², were presented in [25]. For CO₂RR to ethanol, high selectivity (>80%) was only achieved at low current densities [36].

A product that has so far not been able to be obtained in CO₂RR with satisfactory selectivity is n-propanol. This may be due to the fact that the two intermediates of CO₂ reduction are CO and HCOO⁻, with only further reduction of the former being able to yield higher hydrocarbons [37]. This problem is not present in the case of direct CO reduction, where HCOO⁻ ions are not produced. Hence, electrochemical reduction of carbon monoxide (CORR) in tandem reactors may be an attractive pathway for the production of higher hydrocarbons, especially n-propanol. The highest CORR selectivity reported to date was 54% at $I_{C_3H_7OH}=71$ mA/cm² [38], while current densities above 100 mA/cm² were reported in [20], among others.

3.2 Electrolytes

The electrolyte plays a key role in the electrolysis process. Together with the electrodes, it forms a cell that allows a series of electrochemical reactions to take place when voltage is applied to the electrodes.

The electrolyte concentration is a particularly important issue from an operational point of view, because the unreacted electrolyte cations are deposited on the cathode. Although a high concentration of electrolyte increases conductivity and improves process parameters, concentrations of up to 1 mole of cesium or potassium cations should be used [21]. The most common electrolytes used in this reaction include KHCO₃ and KOH. In contrast, KCl, K₂SO₄ or NaHCO₃ are used less frequently [35].

Due to the possibility of hydrogen evolution reaction, more alkaline environments are advantageous. Despite the alkaline environment seems to be more reasonable, in the reaction process, OH⁻ anions and carbon dioxide molecules will generate carbonates/bicarbonates, which can increase the impedance of the cell and block the diffusion channel. This can also lead to irreversible acidification of the electrolyte [39]. In the same source,

the authors also emphasize that the problem of carbonate/bicarbonate formation in a zero-gap electrolyser operating on the KOH electrolyte is difficult to solve, and the use of neutral electrolytes is proposed. In addition to this, neutral electrolytes (usually KHCO₃ solutions) can increase the stability of the electrolyser, as the carbonate/bicarbonate reacts with the protons generated at the anode and releases CO₂ again, which ensures a balance between the cathode and the anode, thus avoiding the irreversible acidification [39].

4. APPLICATIONS

Decarbonisation of many industrial sectors through carbon capture and/or storage technologies is technically possible. However, the biggest challenge, seems to be the further utilisation of this gas, especially since it is produced in quantities that are very difficult to store on a large scale. This means that large-scale carbon dioxide reduction technologies could significantly contribute to the efficient use of this gas. Examples of technologies from which CO₂ can be obtained include:

- CCS (Carbon Capture and Storage) - Carbon dioxide is separated from the exhaust gas after the combustion process.
- Oxy fuel combustion - The exhaust gases contain almost only carbon dioxide, so the need for a separation process is avoided.

The course of the CO₂ reduction reaction depends on many variables, the most important of which are the type of electrolyte, catalysts and process parameters. Due to this, the final products in this process may be different. The most frequently obtained include:

- formic acid - considered a potential fuel substrate for use in low-temperature fuel cells; it can be produced from CO₂ with two main technologies: electrochemical reduction of CO₂ or hydrogenation of CO₂ [40];
- carbon monoxide - a colorless and odorless gas; it is a product of incomplete combustion and a valued chemical reagent that can be used, for example, as a gas for synthesis. It can also be combusted;
- methane - a high-calorific flammable gas used in many sectors of industry, including heating, power, and heavy industry.
- methanol - primarily used as an intermediate in the production of formaldehyde, acetic acid and methyl tert-butyl ether. It has been used as an oxidized fuel additive and also as an alternative transport fuel, in addition to its use as a solvent [41];
- ethanol - a flammable, colourless liquid with a wide range of applications in industry;

- n-propanol - a colourless, water mixable alcohol with a very promising potential in the energy sector and industry. It is possible that it may also become one of the important elements in the decarbonisation of road transport, because as a flammable substance it can be co-combusted with traditional fuels. According to [42], it has excellent disinfectant, cleaning and degreasing properties. The authors also point out that it can be used in spark engines without major modifications, but is not widely used due to high production costs. The authors [42] demonstrate the beneficial aspects of the use of propanol in a spark engine both in environmental and operational terms at their test stand. The tested engine, as a result of co-combustion of the propanol admixture, was characterized by reduced soot emission, however, despite this fact, there may also be some defects, e.g. a slight reduction in the stability of the engine operation at certain ranges of propanol admixture.
- ethylene - the first compound in the homologous series of alkenes; it is a colourless gas with a sweetish odour that has the property of accelerating the ripening of fruit and is practically used for this purpose. It is also used as an anesthetic.

5. SUMMARY

In light of the ongoing energy transition and the need to find alternative energy sources, electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide appears to be a future technology for the production of fuels and industrial reagents. The process can be driven by renewable energy sources and can draw CO₂ from the atmosphere, thus enabling the production of zero-carbon energy carriers. The potential for integrating electrochemical carbon dioxide reduction reactors into the power system seems to be very high, especially in consideration of the fact that the trend is towards increasing the share of RES in the energy mix and growing periodic electricity surpluses because of this. The vision of electrolysers for CO₂ reduction powered by renewable energy seems very distant, especially considering the fact of the large amount of research still needed on this technology. Despite this fact, small-scale industrial installations are not in a distant future, and the first commercial solutions are already available on the market.

Currently, the technology has reached a relatively high maturity only for simple products such as carbon monoxide and formic acid. The production of particularly valuable C₂₊ products, is not economically justified at the current state of development. Hence, further research is needed on the road to implementing CO₂RR.

The main direction of current work is the search for new catalysts capable of reducing CO₂ with satisfactory selectivity and high current density. These catalysts

should be characterized by a long lifetime, be as cheap as possible, and easy to produce. Particular attention is paid to copper-based catalysts, as copper is currently considered to be the only material capable of highly selective CO₂ reduction to C₂₊ compounds. One of the most promising direction of research is electrochemical reduction of carbon monoxide in tandem reactors, where by dividing the process into two reactors, it is possible to obtain higher selectivity, especially for n-propanol.

Nowadays, there is a strong emphasis on the decarbonisation of the transport sector; in the European Union alone, numerous documents are being implemented to oblige Member States to reduce the negative impact of

transport on the climate. For this reason, n-propanol may become an alternative to electric cars if further work on its large-scale production is successful. It is necessary to work not only on the possible adaptation of the construction of modern engines to the combustion of propanol, but also on limiting its price so that it becomes a competitive substitute for gasoline.

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ELEKTROCHEMICZNA REDUKCJA CO₂ WE WSPÓLczesnej ENERGETYCE JAKO METODA PRODUKCJI PROPANOLU I INNYCH PALIW ALTERNATYWNYCH

Słowa kluczowe: elektrochemia, elektroliza, elektrochemiczna redukcja CO₂, nowoczesne technologie energetyczne, produkcja etanolu, metanolu, etylenu, n-propanolu, metanu.

Streszczenie. Artykuł opisuje podstawowe aspekty procesu elektrochemicznej redukcji dwutlenku węgla oraz wykorzystywane w nim katalizatory i elektrolity. W dalszej części pracy poruszono zagadnienie zastosowania tej technologii, omawiając możliwe produkty konwersji. Proces elektrochemicznej redukcji dwutlenku węgla, z uwagi na obecny postęp w jej rozwoju, wydaje się być obiecującym sposobem zagospodarowania tego gazu, szczególnie biorąc pod uwagę obecne trendy związane z dekarbonizacją wielu sektorów przemysłu oraz poszukiwaniem nowych metod utylizacji CO₂. Od momentu wynalezienia tej technologii, postęp w budowie reaktorów i odkrycie nowych katalizatorów sprawiły, że proces – przy odpowiednich parametrach - może być uzasadniony ekonomicznie dla prostych produktów, takich jak tlenek węgla oraz kwas mrówkowy. Jednakże, zanim proces ten znajdzie zastosowanie przemysłowe w produkcji szczególnie pożądaných węglowodorów, takich jak propanol czy etylen, konieczne są dalsze prace badawcze.

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